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Mission possible: food for all
through appropriate plant protection

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ABSTRACTS

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Poster Presentations
Plant Pathogen Interactions

Table 1: Malformation scale among date palm borer adults treated with the isolates MARD 46 and 34.

Isolate MARD 34				
Days after treatment	Concentration			
	1×10^5	1×10^7	1×10^9	1×10^{11}
20 Days	-	-	+	+
23 Days	+	++	++	++
27 Days	++	+++	+++	++++
Isolate MARD 46				
20 Days	-	-	-	+
23 Days	+	-	++	++
27 Days	++	+	+++	-

Scale: +: Low malformed adults; ++: Moderate malformed adults; +++: High malformed adults; ++++: The highest malformed adults

Figure 1

Figure 2: Survival percentages among date palm borer larvae treated with the isolate MARD34 during the experiment duration (29 days).

P PPI 83

Host plant resistance (HPR) traits of watermelon [*Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Mansf.] against melon fruit fly (*Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in hot arid region of India

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The significant differences were found in tested varieties/ genotypes for fruit infestation and larval density per fruit. The varieties/ genotypes, Asahi Yamato (12.73%), AHW/BR-16 (15.10%) and Thar Manak (18.27%) were found resistant; Durgapura Lal (23.03%), Sugar Baby (26.67%), AHW/BR-12 (29.73%), Arka Manik (34.15%), Charleston Grey (38.70%), AHW-65 (35.80%), AHW-19 (48.97%) were found moderately resistant and IC 582909 (53.18%), AHW/BR-60 (55.52%), BSM-1 (59.10%), AHW/BR-137 (60.58%) and AHW/BR-9 (67.37%) were found the susceptible varieties/ genotypes to fruit fly infestation. The significant positive correlation ($r = 0.99$ $p < 0.01$) was observed between per cent fruit infestation and larval density per fruit. The percent fruit infestation and larval density had significant positive correlation with fruit length ($r=0.57$ & 0.55) and days to first fruit harvest ($r=0.75$ & 0.76) and negative correlation with length of ovary pubescence ($r= -0.91$ & -0.91), rind hardness ($r= -0.86$ & -0.87) and rind thickness ($r= -0.77$ & -0.75). Maximum variation in fruit infestation and larval density was explained by length of ovary pubescence (82.50 and 83.60%, respectively) followed by fruit length (4.3 and 3.0% respectively) and rind thickness (3.2 and 2.0%, respectively). Free amino acid was lowest in resistant (Asahi Yamato) and highest in susceptible variety/ genotype (BSM-1) whereas phenols, tannin, total alkaloids and flavonoid contents were highest in resistant and lowest in susceptible varieties/ genotypes. Flavonoid and total alkaloid contents explained (88.4 and 92.0%, respectively) of the total variation in fruit fly infestation and in larval density per fruit. Thus, from the foregoing account, it can be argued that reduction in fruit fly infestations on resistant varieties/ genotypes could be due to antixenotics (biophysical) and antibiosis (allelochemicals). Certain biophysical traits (e.g. length of ovary pubescence, rind hardness and rind thickness) and biochemical traits (e.g. flavonoid, tannins, phenols, ascorbic acid and total alkaloids) were linked to resistance of watermelon against *B. cucurbitae* and therefore, can be used as marker traits in plant breeding programmes to select resistant varieties/ genotypes.